

Studies on Ammonium Phospho-Selenitomolybdate and its Compounds

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Ammonium phospho-selenitomolybdate $4(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot 1.5\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{SeO}_3 \cdot 8\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and its salts with $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, AgNO_3 and guanidine hydrochloride have been prepared and their properties studied. The absorptions of the salts in the Infrared region have also been recorded and attempts have been made to assign the characteristic peaks in the IR spectra of the above salts. Thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis techniques have been used in studying solid state decomposition reactions in air over the temperature range 30° to 600°C .

Several heterotri-polyacid salts containing P_2O_5 , V_2O_5 and MoO_3 are reported in the literature. W. Gibbs¹ prepared two ammonium phosphovanadomolybdates by boiling ammonium phosphomolybdate with ammonium vanadate solution assigning them the following formulae: $8(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 8\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 14\text{MoO}_3 + 50\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $7(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 48\text{MoO}_3 + 30\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Later W. Blum² confirmed Gibbs' view that condensation of P_2O_5 , V_2O_5 and MoO_3 is possible and isolated $5(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 11\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 11\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 50\text{H}_2\text{O}$. No heterotrisalt of phosphorus, molybdenum and selenium has been reported. The present investigation has been carried out with a view to studying the mode of reaction between selenium dioxide, ammonium phosphate and molybdic acid in ammoniacal medium.

This communication records the results of the preparation and analysis of ammonium phospho-selenitomolybdate and its salts with various cations. Thermogravimetric (T.G.A.) and differential thermal (D.T.A.) analysis are also used in conjunction with the infrared spectroscopy to investigate the nature of decomposition and structure of these compounds by observing loss of (a) water molecules and (b) volatile material as the temperature was increased.

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

All the chemicals used were of E. Merck's or B.D.H. pure quality.

Ammonium phospho-selenitomolybdate

4.5 gm. of selenium dioxide, 21 gm. of molybdic acid and 6 gm. of ammonium phosphate were dissolved in liquor ammonia and refluxed for 14 hours. The clear solution thus obtained was evaporated to small volume and then acidified with acetic acid to pH 3-4. On keeping for four days white crystalline powder appeared which could not be

1. W. Gibbs, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1883, 5, 391.
2. W. Blum, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 30, 1858.

recrystallized. It is stable at room temperature, but decomposes when heated. It is soluble in water, but insoluble in organic solvents.

Found: $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}$, 10.57; P_2O_5 , 10.83; SeO_3 , 5.55; MoO_3 , 58.14; H_2O , 14.86. Calcd. for $4(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot 1.5\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{SeO}_3 \cdot 8\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$: $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}$, 10.65; P_2O_5 , 10.72; SeO_3 , 5.58; MoO_3 , 57.8; H_2O , 14.58%.

Lead phospho-selenitomolybdate

It is a white powder, insoluble in water and alcohol and prepared by adding aqueous solution of lead nitrate to ammonium salt solution.

Found: PbO , 37.7; P_2O_5 , 8.94; SeO_3 , 4.53; MoO_3 , 46.8; H_2O , 1.56. Calcd. for $4\text{PbO} \cdot 1.5\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{SeO}_3 \cdot 8\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$: PbO , 37.1; P_2O_5 , 8.85; SeO_3 , 4.61; MoO_3 , 47.8; H_2O , 1.6%.

Silver phospho-selenitomolybdate

When aqueous silver nitrate solution was added to the ammonium salt solution a yellowish white compound separated out.

Found: Ag_2O , 36.2; P_2O_5 , 8.46; SeO_3 , 4.30; MoO_3 , 44.83; H_2O , 5.59. Calcd. for $4\text{Ag}_2\text{O} \cdot 1.5\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{SeO}_3 \cdot 8\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Ag_2O , 36.4; P_2O_5 , 8.32; SeO_3 , 4.33; MoO_3 , 45.4; H_2O , 5.64%.

FIG. 1

Guanidine phospho-selenitomolybdate

It is a white crystalline compound, prepared by adding aqueous guanidine hydrochloride solution to ammonium salt solution and keeping it for an hour.

Found: $(\text{CH}_6\text{N}_3)_2\text{O}$, 26.13; P_2O_5 , 8.26; SeO_2 , 5.31; MoO_3 , 56.12; H_2O , 4.18. Calcd. for $4(\text{CH}_6\text{N}_3)_2\text{O} \cdot 1.6\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 8\text{SeO}_2 \cdot 8\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: $(\text{CH}_6\text{N}_3)_2\text{O}$, 26.34; P_2O_5 , 8.13; SeO_2 , 5.37; MoO_3 , 55.80; H_2O , 4.36%.

Analysis: For the estimation of ammonia the original sample was treated with an excess of sodium hydroxide and the liberated ammonia distilled into a standard solution of hydrochloric acid. The excess acid was titrated with standard sodium hydroxide and the results calculated in terms of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}$. Molybdenum was estimated as MoO_3 , selenium by precipitating as metallic selenium, lead as PbSO_4 , silver as AgCl , phosphorus as $\text{Mg}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$, and water by difference. In the case of guanidine salt carbon and hydrogen were estimated by Pregel's Micro-combustion method and nitrogen by Duma's method.

Thermal Studies. The thermal behaviour of a few salts was studied by differential thermal and thermogravimetric analysis.

The T.G.A. studies were carried out by Stanton Thermobalance (high temperature model) of 10 mg. sensitivity. A heating rate of 3°C per min. was employed with a sample size ranging from 150-170 mesh. Loss in weight was within 2% of the theoretical values in all the cases. The differential thermal analysis apparatus employed in this work consists of an analytical furnace, a transformer and recording equipment. Specimen holders made of sintered alumina have the dimensions $1'' \times 3/4'' \times 1/4''$. A heating rate of 10°C per min. was employed with a sample size ranging from 100-120 mesh. For D.T.A. study the sample was well mixed with extrapure alumina (E. Merck's) and tightly packed in one cell whereas alumina alone as reference material was taken in the other.

Infrared spectrum (in the range of 2-15 microns) was recorded on a Perkin Elmer infracord using potassium bromide disc technique.

TABLE I
Infrared spectra of the compounds Wave numbers (cm.⁻¹)

Ammonium salt	Heated ammonium salt	Lead salt	Silver salt	Guanidine salt
2400 (s)	3060 (b)	3400 (s)	3450 (s)	3360 (s)
3130 (s)				3110 (s)
1640 (w)	1750 (b)	1620 (w)	1620 (m)	1750 (s)
				1800 (m)
1400 (s)	1380 (m)			1490 (m)
1100 (m)	1040 (m)	1040 (s)	1000 (s)	1090 (m)
1040(m)				1050 (m)
				1030 (m)
985 (m)	950 (b)			990 (m)
900 (m)	860 (b)	900 (b)	910 (b)	900 (b)
	770 (b)			

s = strong; m=medium; w=weak and b =broad

DISCUSSION

The composition of the salts have been given on the basis of analytical results. Owing to the large size of the molecule, these compounds could not be characterised. However, the thermal behaviours of these compounds have been studied by both the

thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis techniques, and attempts have been made to assign the absorption bands in the IR spectra of the above salts.

D.T.A. and T.G.A. have provided information on the loss of water from these compounds, and the temperature at which this occurs has been a guide to distinguishing loosely bound water from structural hydroxyl groups. The T.G.A. curve of the ammonium salt reveals that the compound loses 7 molecules of water at 130°C and 4 at 250°C and the rest in the temperature range from 250°-445°C. However, no accurate values for the loss of remaining water could be obtained as the decomposition of the compound occurred simultaneously. The D.T.A. curve is in good agreement with T.G.A. curve and shows two endotherms at 115° and 235°C. The exothermic peak at 320°C can be attributed to the lattice transition^{3,4}. Similar peak is observed in the case of lead phosphoselenitomolybdate. The exotherms at 420°, 520° and 610°C are due to oxidation of ammonia released at the surface of molybdenum oxide through its catalytic action^{4,5}. The absence of exotherms in the case of lead salt confirms the above fact.

FIG. 2

The infrared spectra are very identical. In the 3μ region ($3450\text{-}3400\text{ cm.}^{-1}$) one peak is observed and can be attributed to O-H stretching vibration of water. In the 8μ region a weak absorption band appears at $1640\text{-}1620\text{ cm.}^{-1}$ which corresponds to bending mode

3. S. Prasad & V. N. Garg, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1965, 38, No. 9, 1633.

4. S. Prasad & V. N. Garg, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan* (communicated).

5. Eikoh Ma: *Ibid.*, 1964, 2, 171-175.

of water. The bands shown at 110-965 cm.^{-1} and found by other workers⁶⁻⁹ are tentatively ascribed to P-O linkage. In the case of lead and silver salt a single band is found, while in ammonium salt strong absorption consisting of multiplet peaks occur over the range 1110-965 cm.^{-1} and is connected to phosphorus-oxygen linkage⁹. The regions of the absorption of Se-O and Mo-O linkages¹⁰ are so close that in the compounds absorption bands of both overlap to a considerable extent to form a broad band round about 900 cm.^{-1} . In the case of ammonium salt the absorbances at 3100 cm.^{-1} and 1400 cm.^{-1} are characteristic for the ammonium radical. The rest of the bands are usual.

The positions of the IR bands of the above salts have been found slightly different in each case and it might have been affected by crystal structure environments, the nature of the positive ions, and the interaction of the lattice frequencies. A difference in the type or extent of hydration also alters some of the frequencies¹¹.

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